

CLINICAL PICTURE OF MEDIAN CYSTS

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Annotation.

Median fistulas and neck cysts are treated only surgically – by radical excision of the fistula course all the way to the root of the tongue. Incomplete excision of the fistula always leads to relapse – this explains the frequent re-admission of patients to the hospital. The patient's position during the operation is on his back, a roller is placed under his shoulders, the head is thrown back in the middle position.

Keywords.

clinical picture, median cysts, surgically, by radical excision, fistula, tongue, neck, embryonic dysplasia, hemostasis.

Median cysts of the neck are anomalies of the development of the gill apparatus and its derivatives, as well as the thyroid and thymus glands. Some authors believe that median cysts and fistulas are embryonic dysplasia associated with non-infection of the thyroid duct 8 (N. A. Gruzdev, 1965; L. R. Episheva, 1972; Bethmann, 1971, etc.). This assumption is supported by the connection of median neck cysts with the hyoid bone and the blind hole of the tongue root, as well as the correspondence of the course of the complete median fistula to the topography of the thyroid rudiment (V. S. Dmitrieva et al., 1968). Sometimes, during histological examination of median cysts and fistulas of the neck, inclusions of thyroid tissue are found in their wall. This confirms their origin from the tissues of the non-reduced thyroid duct.

CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MEDIAN NECK CYSTS

The formation grows slowly, manifests itself in the form of a rounded protrusion along the midline between the hyoid bone and the upper edge of the thyroid cartilage, painless with palpation. With atypical localization, the median cyst is located in the submandibular triangle, maintaining a connection with the hyoid bone. The skin above the cysts is not changed, it is freely movable, the

boundaries of the formation are clear, the consistency is testy, the formation shifts quite well to the side and upwards. Mobility downwards is limited due to the connection with the hyoid bone, during the act of swallowing, the cyst shifts upwards together with the hyoid bone. When the cyst communicates with the oral cavity through the preserved thyroid duct, its size decreases after the contents are released into the oral cavity. Inflammation of the median and lateral cysts occurs in 60% of patients (V. S. Dmitrieva et al., 1968), which is explained by colds or infection penetration through the blind hole of the tongue root in stomatitis. Clinically, this is manifested by pain when swallowing, painful, without clear boundaries infiltration in the thickness of the tongue. With spontaneous autopsy and non-radical surgical intervention, after the elimination of inflammation phenomena, a functioning median fistula of the neck remains (Fig. 1). Fig. 1. Inflamed median cyst of the neck, median fistula. Condition after surgical treatment, rubber drainage in the wound 9 Median fistulas are divided into complete and incomplete (the latter are external and internal). The external opening of the complete median and incomplete external fistula opens on the anterior surface of the neck along the midline between the hyoid bone and the upper tenderloin of thyroid cartilage, at or above the bone (Fig. 2). Fig. 2. Median cyst of the neck. The probe is located in the external opening of the incomplete external median fistula of the neck, complete and incomplete external fistulas are clinically manifested in the form of a granulating wound of small size, covered with a bloody crust, after removal of which and compression of the fistula, a mucopurulent discharge can be obtained. The skin in the area of the external fistula is scarred, retracted. During palpation, a dense weight is determined, going from the fistula to the hyoid bone, which shifts with it during swallowing movements. When the hole is closed, pain and swelling appear in this area. A complete fistula passes from the external mouth through subcutaneous fat, the broad subcutaneous muscle of the neck and the superficial leaf of the cervical fascia, without having lateral branches. Further, it is most often attached to the anterior or upper edge of the hyoid bone and pierces its body. Behind the hyoid bone, a complete fistula continues through the muscles of the bottom of the oral cavity and tongue obliquely upwards and opens into the area of the root of the tongue at its blind opening. In this area, the fistula may have blind lateral branches, which is often the cause of relapses with non-radical removal. Incomplete median internal fistula of the neck arises from the unreduced remnants of the thyroid duct, is located above the hyoid bone, and its opening is located in a typical place – the area of the blind from- 10 verst of the

tongue. Such fistulas do not manifest themselves clinically, because the outflow of the contents occurs freely into the oral cavity through the blind hole.

TREATMENT OF MEDIAN NECK CYSTS

Median fistulas and neck cysts are treated only surgically – by radical excision of the fistula course all the way to the root of the tongue. Incomplete excision of the fistula always leads to relapse – this explains the frequent re-admission of patients to the hospital. The patient's position during the operation is on his back, a roller is placed under his shoulders, the head is thrown back in the middle position. It is preferable to perform the operation under endotracheal anesthesia, because a significant injury is inflicted on the patient, and in some cases, surgical intervention to isolate the fistula is prolonged. Before the incision, in order not to lose the direction of the fistula during the operation, a solution of methylene blue is poured into it. The incision is made at the lower edge of the fistula parallel to the skin fold of the neck. Dissect the skin, subcutaneous tissue and superficial fascia with subcutaneous muscle. Fabrics are separated from the bottom up. The fistula course is gradually excised to the hyoid bone, through the body of which it usually passes and follows further into the depth. The body of the hyoid bone is resected at the site of the passage of the fistula. At the same time, it is important not to lose the further course of the fistula. If the direction of the fistula is not determined above the hyoid bone, it is necessary to fill the fistula passage with a solution of methylene blue before partial resection of the hyoid bone. To facilitate further excision of the fistula, the anterior abdomen of the bicuspid muscle is crossed. The edges of the wound are hooked apart. Gradually, the fistula is separated. It is necessary to make sure that his move is not lost in the scar adhesions. Sometimes the fistula passage can be felt by its compaction. Excision often ends at the root of the zygote in the area of the blind hole, where it sometimes has a funnel shape. When allocating a fistula in the area of the passage of the chin-hyoid muscles, it should be remembered about the proximity of the lingual arteries. After isolation and excision of the fistula passage, final hemostasis is carried out throughout its entire length, the tissues of the bottom of the oral cavity are infiltrated with a solution of antibiotics, immersion sutures are applied with a catgut. A rubber graduate is left between the skin sutures, which is removed after two days (Fig. 3). In the presence of significant scar adhesions along the course of the median fistula, its isolation is sometimes very difficult and leads to great trauma to the tissues of the bottom of the oral cavity and tongue. In these cases, taking into account the subsequent development of postoperative edema, it is advisable to sometimes perform a tracheotomy for preventive purposes.

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